

Prevalence and risk factors for OTITIS MEDIA with Effusion in Preschool Children in Janakpur, Nepal

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Abstract: Janakpur is a city thickly populated and is situated in the Southern Part of Nepal. It lies in the Terai adjacent to India (Bihar)-Nepal- India boarder. OTITIS MEDIA with Effusion (OME) is a condition in which there is fluid in the middle ear but no signs of acute infection. As fluid builds up in the middle ear and Eustachian tube, it places pressure on the tympanic membrane. OTITIS MEDIA with effusion (OME) is a collection of non-infected fluid in the middle ear space. It is also called serous or Secretary OTITIS MEDIA (SOM). This fluid may accumulate in the middle ear as a result of a cold, sore throat or upper respiratory infection. Mainly it is present in the area where there is malnutrition in children and they are not properly cared. Its prevalence is seen in preschool age children and frequently noticed in Janakpur, Nepal. Home remedies include applying a warm compress and inhaling steam, but over-the-counter medicines may also work to open the ear canals and drain the fluid. If these methods don't help, though, the patients should seek medical attention to have the fluid drained. If delayed in treatment, more risk factors may come into notice. The author has tried to find the causes of Effusion and its control in the prevalent area and suggest the concerned authorities for controlling these issues. The preschools of Janakpur were taken as population. The sample size of 150 was taken for the investigation purpose and suitable statistical tools were used for sample analysis to make the findings more reliable.

Keywords: OTITIS MEDIA, Effusion, Risk factor, Preschool children.

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Introduction

Janakpur is a city thickly populated and is situated in the Southern Part of Nepal. It lies in the Terai adjacent to India (Bihar) - Nepal- India boarder. The syndrome known as OTITIS MEDIA with effusion (OME) is characterized by middle ear fluid without any indications of an acute infection. The tympanic membrane is compressed as fluid accumulates in the middle ear and Eustachian tube. A accumulation of non-infected fluid in the middle ear area is

known as OTITIS MEDIA with effusion (OME). It is also called serous or SECRETORY OTITIS MEDIA (SOM). An upper respiratory illness, sore throat, or cold can cause this fluid to build up in the middle ear. Mainly it is present in the area where there is malnutrition in children and they are not properly cared. Its prevalence is seen in preschool age children and frequently noticed in Janakpur, Nepal. (Searight, Singh, & Peterson., 2023)

Some of the home remedies include applying a warm compress and inhaling steam, but over-the-counter medicines may also work to open the ear canals and drain the fluid. If these methods don't help, though, you should seek medical attention to have the fluid drained and cured timely.

It typically arises when the Eustachian tubes are not functioning normally. The most common bacteria isolated from the middle ear in AOM (Acute OTITIS Media) are *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, hemophilic influenza, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Other terms related to OME include-

- OTITIS media with effusion,
- Chronic supportive otitis media, (CSOM) and
- Adhesive OTITIS media.

The main causal organism of Otitis Media Effusion is bacteria. Acute Otitis Media (AOM), Otitis Media with Effusion (OME; "glue ear"), and Chronic Supportive Otitis Media (CSOM) are among the several conditions that make up Otitis Media (OM), sometimes known as middle ear inflammation. One of the most prevalent illnesses affecting young children globally is OM. (WHO) An abnormal collection of fluid in hollow spaces or between tissues of the body. For example, a pleural effusion is a collection of fluid between the two layers of membrane covering the lung simply referred as Effusion.

Effusion means an instance of giving off something such as liquid or gas - a massive effusion of poisonous gas. A non-purulent effusion of the middle ear, which can be either mucoid or serous, is a characteristic of OTITIS Media with Effusion (OME). Aural fullness or hearing loss are the most common symptoms; pain or fever are rarely present. In children, hearing loss is often moderate and is often discovered only with an audiogram. Serious One particular kind of OTITIS media has effusion brought on by transudation formation, which happens when middle ear pressure rapidly drops in comparison to ambient pressure. In this instance, the fluid is transparent and watery.

The researchers and readers must understand the difference between media with effusion and other forms of middle ear infection is important. OTITIS media is a generic term defined as an inflammation of the middle ear without reference to a specific etiology (Causes) or pathogenesis. Any inflammation shows symptoms like redness, hotness, painfulness and swelling. (Higgins, 2024).

OME is also called glue ear, is characterized by a collection of fluid in the middle-ear cleft. OME has been noticed in Janakpur for long time and it is prevalent in preschool level children in the place vicinity causing the temporary hearing loss in affected children. Efforts have been made in local levels too to control OME.

Daycare, the number of siblings, smoking, breastfeeding, birth weight, socioeconomic level (SES), and air pollution were the main risk factors for OM. Internationally, OM is managed differently. For instance, the prevalence of antibiotic prescriptions varies from 31% in the Netherlands to over 90% in several other Western nations.

Review of Literature

Prakash conducted a research titled as "Pattern of ear diseases in rural school children: experiences of free health camps in Nepal". He concluded that Wax followed by chronic supportive otitis media and otitis media with effusion were the most common ear diseases in rural school children of Nepal. Reducing the frequency of ear illnesses would require improvements in socioeconomic level and health care services, such as reiterating free health camps.

Maharjan, Bhandari, Singh, Mishra conducted a research entitled as "Prevalence of OTITIS media in school going children in Eastern Nepal". Following a thorough analysis, they discovered that primary ear care instruction for educators, learners, and parents can stop hearing damage in these susceptible kids. School based study could be one of the useful and cost-effective modality aimed at community oriented program.

Bagshaw, Wall, Dowswell, Martin, and Smith incepted an inquiry under the title of "Hearing impairment in OTITIS media with effusion: a cross-sectional study based in Pokhara, Nepal" and they came into conclusion that Hearing Impairment (HI) is a common complication of OME in Nepal. There is previously unreported heterogeneity in the number of OME patients complicated by HI amongst communities. Their study identified higher rates of morbidity amongst rural populations but was unable to identify associated factors.

Martines, Martines, Sciacca, Otolaryngol (2011) conducted their studies under the topic "Otitis media with effusion with or without atopy: audiological findings on primary schoolchildren". Their studies revealed that the higher prevalence of OME in atopic children and the statistically significant differences in audiometric and tympanometric measurements among atopic and nonatopic subjects suffering from OME suggest the important role of allergy in the genesis and recurrence of OME.

Gultekin, Develioğlu, Yener, Ozdemir, Külekçi (2009) did a research titled as "Prevalence and risk factors for persistent OTITIS media with effusion in primary school children in Istanbul, Turkey". This was the study taken for the purpose of knowing the abroad studies and its findings. After the detailed examination, they concluded that Environmental, epidemiologic and familial factors in the etiology of OME are important. It is necessary to educate the parents about the signs and risk factors of OME in order to avoid the condition from developing or from being diagnosed too late, which might result in irreversible hearing loss.

Another ROL was taken from China. Tong, Yue, Ku, Lo, Wong, Hasselt (2006), these authors conducted a study under the topic "Risk factors for otitis media with effusion in Chinese schoolchildren: a nested case-control study and review of the literature" and their conclusion was Risk factors identified in the Chinese schoolchildren for OME were comparable with previous western reports. One of the main causes of middle ear effusion was a prior episode of acute OTITIS media.

Author links open overlay panel Rovers, de Kok, Schilde (2006) jointly conducted a study as "Risk factors for otitis media: An international perspective" and they concluded that the differences in risk factor exposure between populations are often overshadowed by other culturally or demographically significant factors. The management of OM may benefit from efforts to identify these characteristics both within and between populations, and they merit more research.

Stockmann, et.al (2013) after their studies concluded that Seasonal RSV, human metapneumovirus, and influenza activity were temporally associated with increased diagnoses of AOM among children. These findings support the role of individual respiratory viruses in the development AOM. These data also underscore the potential for respiratory viral vaccines to reduce the burden of AOM.

Methodology of Research

Objectives of the Study: The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of OME in primary school children, in Janakpur, Nepal.

Design: Cross-sectional survey

Study duration: Feb. 2019 to Jan. 2020

Setting: Five large randomly selected urban schools in Janakpur, Nepal was taken as population. From the population under study, 150 students of different age groups were taken in into consideration for the investigation to detect prevalence of glue ear.

Subjects: All children in the stages of nursery, LKG and UKG (3-8 years) were considered as subjects.

Data collection: Each child was asked a few questions with the help of questionnaire.

Clinical examination with an Otoscope and Tympanometer was also conducted with the help of medical practitioners employed in the local hospitals.

Research Gaps: The fresh research reports are very scanty in this field and are not even available. Hardly research conducted are found before 2009. Thereafter, there are no proven records of the fresh studies. Manly the research is

conducted taking the prevalent risk factors associated therein. These include age of the children; mainly the children between 6 months to 2 years are more likely to get infected. Family hereditary factor is also common factor. Day care attendance, No of Children, Ethnicity Factors, parents Tobacco smoking, by exposure to secondary smokers causing smoky environment, pacifier uses, long time bottle milk feeding, allergy and season are the main prevalent risk factors associated with Otitis media. Some studies include- age, parents heredity factors, day care attendance, parents Tobacco smoking, allergy cases are seen taken under studies by the different scholars in different times.

So, some of the left prevalent risk factors like (WHO)

1. Age of the children,
2. No of Children,
3. Ethnicity Factors,
4. Pacifier uses,
5. Long time bottle milk feeding and
6. Season are taken as research gaps to make this inquiry.

Result and Discussion

Total 150 children were consulted for the study and it is tabulated as hereunder for the purpose of analysis and drawing the valid inference. Ages of the children were ranging from 3 Years to 8 years.

Table 1: Age of Children.

S. No.	Age	No of Children	OME %
1	8	21	14
2	7	25	17
3	6	30	20
4	5	32	22
5	4	41	27
6	3	1	0.007= 0
Total	-	150	100 %

Table 1 showed that the highest cases of OTITIS was noticed in the age category of 4 years followed by age class of 5 years and then 6, 7, and eight years of age of children. This indicated that as the age goes on increasing the OTITIS media occurrence goes on decreasing. This further clarifies that either the growing children are taking care or, may be, they are reporting to their parents in time which led to less occurrence of the OTITIS.

Table 2: No. of Children.

S. No.	Family Surveyed	No. of Children	OME %
1	60	25	4
2	60	53	15
3	60	40	22
4	60	21	31
5	60	8	19
6	60	3	9
Total	360	150	100%

Above table 2 was formed to see the effect of number of children on occurrence of OTITIS MEDIA. A survey was conducted in 360 families and number of children were seen therein. After analysis it clearly revealed that high

occurrence of OTITIS that 31% was noticed in the children group of 21. It was followed by 22% OTITIS occurrence was seen in the children group of 40. This explains that there is no effect of number of children in OTITIS MEDIA occurrence in children. This may be indicating that proper care is the way to get rid of OTITIS.

Table 3: Ethnicity Factor of the Subjects

S. No.	Ethnicity Factor	No .of Children	OME %
1	Aryan	95	43
2	Mongolian	55	57
Total	-----	150	100 %

Another table was formed; Table 3 to see the effects of ethnicity factor in OTITIS occurrence in Children of Janakpur. The Aryans in the sample were 95 and the Mongolian children in the sample was 55. The OME in Mongol was found 57% and it was 43% in Aryan. This indicates that Aryan are more cautious in children care in their preschool time.

Table 4: Pacifiers Users.

S. No.	Pacifiers	No. of Children	OME%
1	Users	113	75
2	Non users	37	25
Total	----	150	100%

Parents in Nepal are, now a days are busy and they are irrespective of gender factor (Karki. M, Vyas. S, and Ghosal. I (2024) are doing job outside the home and female are also equally coming out of their home for job. In the absence of their parents, the baby attendants are asked to use pacifiers. The pacifiers are, after our test, were found to affect in OME Occurrence. In the test it was found that more the pacifiers users, more the occurrence. It may be logical that the pacifiers might be contaminated and sometimes may drop in the ear also which may occur the OME. In 113 users, 75 % were the occurrence of OME.

Table 5: Long Time Bottle Milk Feeding

S. No.	Bottle Milk Feeding	No. of Children	OME%
1	Feeders	44	20
2	Non Feeders	106	71
Total	----	150	100%

Table 5 is formed to see the effects of long time Bottle Milk Feeding. Breast milk is the ideal food for infants. It is safe, clean and contains antibodies which help protect against many common childhood illnesses (WHO). Breastfeeding is one of the most effective ways to ensure child health and survival. However, contrary to WHO recommendations, fewer than half of infants under 6 months old are exclusively breastfed.

This study shows that in Breastfed children lower percentage i.e. only 20 % OME cases were occurred as against of 71 % in non- breastfed child. This may be due to lack of immunity that is provided with mothers' fresh milk which even contains antibiotic to immunize the children.

Table 6: Season

S. No.	Season	No. of Children	OME%
1	Winter (November - February)	47	32
2	Summer (March -May)	38	25
3	Rainy (June- October)	65	43
Total	--	150	100%

Table 6 serves the purpose of checking the effects of season on the occurrence of OME in the preschool children of Janakpur based Preschools. Mainly three seasons namely winter, summer and rainy seasons were taken on reference to study the seasonal effects on OME occurrence. The detailed study clearly depicted that rainy was the main season of OME occurrence in Janakpur followed by winter and summer seasons respectively. This may be because in rainy season the flooded water may be contaminated, in winter the children in the Janakpur area are not getting hygiene condition and they are not even taking bath for months. The similar type of results are also reported in the research entitled as "Prevalence of acute OTITIS media in a tertiary care center of Assam " by these authors - Mili, Talukdar, Sarmah, Saiki. This result is justifiable.

Home remedies in OTTIS MEDIA treatment include applying a warm compress and inhaling steam, Is it really effective in controlling the sickness? An attempt is made here to test effectiveness of home remedies' using Chi-Square test. Our surveyors got the following information in using and not using the local home treatment in OTITIS MEDIA control by visiting the children's family in Janakpur vicinity area. Chi-Square test was formed for making decision.

Table 7: Local Treatment Effectiveness Checking

Treatment	Cured (Not Attacked)	Not Cured (Attacked)	Total
Home treatment Applied	469	31	500
Home treatment not Applied	1315	185	1500
Total	1784	216	2000

Calculations-

Observed (O)	Expected (E)	O- E	(O-E) ²	O-E) ² /E
469	446	23	529	1.18609
31	54	-23	529	9.7962
1315	1338	-23	529	0.3953
185	162	23	529	3.2654
			Total	14.643

Df, here is calculated as -

$$(r-1) (c-1)$$

$$= (2-1) (2-1)$$

$$= 1$$

HO: The home treatment is not effective

H1: The home treatment is effective

The tab. Chi-square value is 3.841 at 5% l.o.s. whereas, calculated value is 14.643 which is bigger than the tab. Value. So, the test is significant. We, can therefore, conclude that home treatment is found effective in controlling the OTITIS MEDIA in early stages if it is applied cautiously.

Conclusion

From the detailed studies the author, here, concludes that in the age category of 4 years followed by age class of 5 years and then 6, 7, and eight years of age of children were respectively susceptible to OTITIS MEDIA. After analysis it also clearly revealed that high occurrence of OTITIS that 31% was noticed in the children group family of 21. It was followed by 22% OTITIS occurrence seen in the children family group category of 40.

While seen in the ethnicity variable, the study on the sample size of Aryans 95 and the Mongolian children in the sample 55, the OME in Mongol was found 57% and it was 43% in Aryan in OTITIS occurrence.

In the test it was also found that more the pacifiers users, there was more the occurrence OTITIS. It may be logical that the pacifiers might be contaminated and sometimes the pacifiers content may drop in the ear also which may occur the OME. In 113 pacifiers users, 75 % were the occurrence of OME as compared to that of 25 % non-users of 37.

In Breastfed children, it was also found that there was lower percentage occurrence of OTITIS i.e. only 20 % OME cases were occurred as against of 71 % in non- breastfed child.

When the researcher tried to see the effects of seasons in OTITIS occurrence, the detailed study clearly depicted that rainy was the main season of OME occurrence in Janakpur followed by winter and summer seasons respectively. This may be justified because in rainy season the flooded water may be contaminated, in winter the children in the Janakpur area are not getting hygiene condition and they are not even taking bath for months.

Finally, the customary locally adopted home treatment practiced as applying a warm compress and inhaling steam and its effects was also seen whether it is effective in controlling the OTITIS occurrence if did cautiously and in the early stage. The Chi-square test was conducted and it was found that home treatment is effective in controlling the OTITIS MEDIA in early stages if it is applied cautiously.

Managerial Implication: The results of the this research can be taken as reference by the parents, medical practitioners and the government personnel making OTITIS MEDIA controlling policy in the Janakpur locality for the effective controlling of OTITIS. The parents can also take the advantages from this results in taking timely care to control this illness in time. They can take the seasonal care of their children, know the advantages of breast feeding and disadvantages of the use of pacifiers to their children. The hospital medical practitioners can also suggest the Janakpur locals to timely take the precautionary measures to control this illness in their areas.

The Future Scope of the Research: The future researcher can conduct further research taking other possible variables of OTITIS MEDIA for more level of knowledge and validity and reliability of the research results.

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